

**EMPOWERING ADOLESCENTS: UNITING PEOPLE FOR TEENAGE
EMPOWERMENT AND ELIMINATION NETWORK IN CARARAYAN NATIONAL HIGH
SCHOOL, NAGA CITY, PHILIPPINES
PROJECT TEEN UP**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13837836>

ABSTRACT

The report encapsulates the focus group discussion conducted as part of the Community Engagement and Exposure (CEE) project, a component of the University of Nueva Caceres' Problem Research Outcome-Based Education (PROBE) program. This initiative, adopted by the School of Graduate Studies, aims to involve graduate students in addressing community needs and developing organizational innovations. The study focuses on raising awareness about teenage pregnancy and providing comprehensive sex education and support services to affected students. Utilizing a Focus Group Discussion (FGD) methodology, stakeholders, including community leaders, school officials, and organizers, engaged in a collaborative needs assessment and brainstorming session. The discussion identified critical challenges in the community, leading to the formulation of a detailed action plan. The results highlighted the importance of multi-stakeholder involvement, clear role definition, and a unified vision for the community service program's successful implementation. This coordinated effort is expected to drive sustainable community development and improve service delivery within Cararayan NHS and its surrounding areas.

Key Words: *Community Engagement, Focus Group Discussion (FGD) PROBE Program, Teenage Pregnancy Awareness, Comprehensive Sex Education, Stakeholder Collaboration, Needs Assessment, Action Plan Development, Support Services for Teenagers, Community Service Program.*

INTRODUCTION

Teenage pregnancy remains a pressing social issue, particularly in developing countries, where it adversely affects both the personal and social prospects of young individuals. In the Philippines, teenage pregnancies continue to rise, contributing to a cycle of poverty, educational deprivation, and health complications for young mothers and their children. This study, conducted as part of the Community Engagement and Exposure (CEE) project under the University of Nueva Caceres' Problem Research Outcome-Based Education (PROBE) program, addresses the issue of teenage pregnancy within the community of Cararayan National High School (NHS). Through a collaborative approach, this project aims to raise awareness, offer comprehensive sex education, and provide support services to teenagers, aligning with the broader objectives of the PROBE program to foster organizational innovation through community engagement.

The community of Cararayan NHS is experiencing a rise in teenage pregnancy, a trend reflective of national patterns. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (2020), the Philippines has one of the highest rates of teenage pregnancy in Southeast Asia. Research indicates that this demographic challenge stems from factors such as limited access to contraceptives, inadequate sex education, and social pressures (Smith, 2017). As Manlove, Mariner, and Romano (2015) highlight, teenage pregnancy often disrupts the academic journey of young women, leading to high dropout rates and diminished future prospects. This context underscores the need for immediate and tailored interventions at the local level.

Existing literature provides a comprehensive understanding of the multi-faceted nature of teenage pregnancy. Manlove et al. (2015) found that teenage mothers are more likely to drop out of school, which leads to long-term economic disadvantages. Similarly, Smith (2017) emphasized that lower socioeconomic status and insufficient access to sexual education are significant contributors to teenage pregnancy. Brown and Bzostek (2016) further elaborated on the psychological consequences, reporting increased levels of depression and anxiety among teen mothers, which underscores the need for mental health support.

Research shows that comprehensive sex education, which includes information about both abstinence and contraception, is more effective in reducing teen pregnancy rates compared to abstinence-only programs. According to Santelli et al. (2017), teens who receive comprehensive sex education are more likely to delay sexual initiation, use contraception, and reduce the number of sexual partners. This approach empowers adolescents by providing them with accurate information and the skills to make informed decisions about their sexual health, ultimately reducing the incidence of unintended pregnancies among teenagers.

Health outcomes for teenage mothers and their children are also a concern, as Kirby (2018) found that teen pregnancies are often associated with higher risks of preterm births and low birth weights. The role of family dynamics is another critical factor, with Jaccard and Dodge (2014) highlighting that teens from single-parent households or homes with

familial conflict are at greater risk of becoming pregnant. Moreover, peer influence, as discussed by Markham et al. (2017), plays a role in shaping teenagers' decisions about sexual activity, emphasizing the importance of peer education programs. Finally, Kirby (2016) demonstrated the effectiveness of comprehensive sex education in reducing teenage pregnancy rates, in contrast to abstinence-only programs.

This study is both timely and necessary, as it addresses the rising incidence of teenage pregnancy in the Cararayan NHS community. While existing literature offers insights into the causes and consequences of teenage pregnancy, there is a lack of research on community-based interventions that involve direct collaboration between educational institutions and local stakeholders. The current project seeks to fill this gap by developing a comprehensive framework for sex education and support services, specifically tailored to the needs of the Cararayan NHS community.

While numerous studies (e.g., Manlove et al., 2015; Kirby, 2018) have examined the outcomes of teenage pregnancy, few have explored the role of multi-stakeholder collaboration in implementing targeted interventions within small community settings. Additionally, most research focuses on the effectiveness of sex education programs but lacks an in-depth understanding of how such programs can be tailored to the unique socio-cultural dynamics of individual communities like Cararayan. This study addresses these gaps by investigating the development of a locally-driven, stakeholder-inclusive approach to reducing teenage pregnancy rates.

The research began with a coordination meeting and a series of focus group discussions in October 2023. The aim was to assess the root causes of teenage pregnancy in Cararayan NHS and to develop a community-driven intervention. The discussions revealed several gaps in sex education, awareness, and support services for teenage mothers. Moving forward, the project will involve the design and implementation of a sex education curriculum tailored to the local context, as well as the development of support mechanisms for pregnant teens. The project will continue over the next six months, with periodic evaluations to measure its effectiveness.

The core issue this study aims to tackle is the high rate of teenage pregnancies at Cararayan NHS, which has significant social, educational, and health implications for young women in the community. Through the collaborative efforts of school administrators, community leaders, and graduate students, this study seeks to implement a comprehensive strategy that combines sex education with support services for teenagers, ultimately reducing teenage pregnancy rates and improving the well-being of the youth in the community.

Research Questions

This aim of this study is to identify how effective was the Project T.E.E.N U.P seminar in achieving its objectives, both in terms of clarity and overall usefulness, as perceived by the participants?

Specific Research Questions:

1. To what extent were the seminar objectives clear to the participants?
2. How well were the seminar objectives achieved by the participants?
3. How did participants evaluate the facilitator's performance in terms of mastery of the topic, ability to sustain interest, welcoming questions and comments, and clarity of speech?
4. Did the seminar meet the expectations of the participants?
5. How valuable did the participants perceive the time spent in the seminar to be?
6. Overall, how useful did participants find the seminar in relation to their expectations and objectives?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive research method, aimed at capturing and presenting the current situation of Cararayan National High School and the surrounding community, particularly focusing on the issue of teenage pregnancy. This approach enabled the researchers to comprehensively assess the socio-cultural, educational, and health-related factors influencing teenage pregnancy. The study served as a foundation for developing targeted interventions to address this issue.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at Cararayan National High School, a newly established public secondary school located in Naga City, Philippines. As a burgeoning institution, Cararayan NHS caters to a diverse student body and is dedicated to providing quality education. The school's evolving nature and commitment to student development made it an ideal setting for examining the challenges and needs of adolescent students, particularly in the area of sexual health and teenage pregnancy.

Sampling Method

The study used a purposive sampling method to select participants for the focus group discussions and survey questionnaires. The sample included both students and faculty members at Cararayan NHS who were directly involved in or affected by the school's sexual health education programs. Students were selected based on their age group (typically those at higher risk for teenage pregnancy), while faculty members were chosen for their roles in supporting the school's initiatives on adolescent health and education.

Demographics

The participants in the study included:

Students: 75 students from Grades 10- 12, aged 14-17, who were identified as the primary beneficiaries of the Teen-Up Project.

Faculty Members: 5 teachers, including guidance counsellors and health educators, who were actively involved in delivering sex education and providing support to students.

School Administrators: Key school officials, including the principal and department heads, who participated in the planning and implementation of the Teen-Up Project.

Data Gathering Procedure

Data were gathered using two primary instruments: questionnaires and focus group discussions (FGDs).

Questionnaires: A structured questionnaire was developed to collect quantitative data on the students' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding sexual health and teenage pregnancy. The questionnaire included sections on demographic information, knowledge of contraception, awareness of the consequences of teenage pregnancy, and access to sexual health resources.

Focus Group Discussions (FGDs): To supplement the quantitative data, FGDs were conducted with students and faculty members to gather in-depth qualitative insights. These discussions explored participants' perceptions of the effectiveness of the Teen-Up Project, their experiences with sexual health education, and the socio-cultural factors influencing teenage pregnancy within the community.

Instruments Used

Questionnaire: The questionnaire was designed to measure the benefits of the seminars given to students for their awareness of TEEN pregnancy.

Understanding of the consequences of teenage pregnancy

Attitudes towards sex education

Access to support services and counselling

FGD Guide: A semi-structured discussion guide was used for the focus group discussions. It included open-ended questions designed to elicit detailed responses about the impact of the Teen-Up Project, the role of the community and school in addressing teenage pregnancy, and recommendations for improvement.

Data Analysis

Data were analysed using a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods.

Quantitative Analysis: The data from the questionnaires were tallied and analysed using descriptive statistics. Percentages and frequency distributions were used to summarize students' knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to sexual health. This provided a

numerical representation of the participants' level of awareness and the effectiveness of the sex education program.

Qualitative Analysis: The data from the focus group discussions were analysed thematically. Responses were categorized into key themes such as effectiveness of the sex education program, challenges faced by students, and community support. This thematic analysis helped to identify patterns and insights into the participants' perceptions and experiences.

Scope and Limitations

Scope: The study focused on assessing the effectiveness of the Teen-Up Project at Cararayan National High School, with particular attention to the knowledge and attitudes of students regarding sexual health and teenage pregnancy. It also examined the role of faculty and school administrators in supporting the initiative. The study primarily targeted Grades 9 and 10 students due to their heightened vulnerability to teenage pregnancy.

Limitations:

The study was limited to a single school, which may reduce the generalizability of the findings to other educational institutions.

The sample size, while sufficient for this setting, was relatively small and may not capture all perspectives within the community.

The study relied on self-reported data, which may be subject to social desirability bias, especially given the sensitive nature of the topics covered.

The timeframe of the study limited its ability to measure long-term outcomes of the intervention, such as actual reductions in teenage pregnancy rates.

Despite these limitations, the study provides valuable insights into how school-based initiatives like the Teen-Up Project can influence students' knowledge and attitudes toward sexual health and teenage pregnancy prevention.

RESULTS

The Project T.E.E.N U.P study aimed to assess the quality and effectiveness of a seminar by evaluating two main aspects: the clarity of the seminar objectives and the extent to which these objectives were fully attained by the participants.

1. Seminar Objectives

Clarity of Seminar Objectives

4 Points: 30 out of 71 participants (42.25%) rated the clarity of the seminar objectives as 4 points.

5 Points: 41 out of 71 participants (57.75%) rated the clarity of the seminar objectives as 5 points.

Attainment of Seminar Objectives

4 Points: 31 out of 71 participants (43.66%) rated the attainment of the seminar objectives as 4 points.

5 Points: 40 out of 71 participants (56.34%) rated the attainment of the seminar objectives as 5 points.

1. Seminar content

Results

Scope of Seminar Content

3 Points: 2 out of 71 participants (2.82%)

4 Points: 28 out of 71 participants (39.44%)

5 Points: 41 out of 71 participants (57.75%)

Quality and Clarity of Presentation

3 Points: 1 out of 71 participants (1.41%)

4 Points: 25 out of 71 participants (35.21%)

5 Points: 45 out of 71 participants (63.38%)

Organization of Topics

3 Points: 1 out of 71 participants (1.41%)

4 Points: 15 out of 71 participants (21.13%)

5 Points: 55 out of 71 participants (77.46%)

Time Allocation

3 Points: 2 out of 71 participants (2.82%)

4 Points: 14 out of 71 participants (19.72%)

5 Points: 55 out of 71 participants (77.46%)

1. Facilitator

The Project T.E.E.N U.P study evaluated the quality and effectiveness of the seminar by focusing on various aspects of the facilitator's performance. Participants rated the facilitator on mastery of the topic, ability to sustain interest, welcoming questions and comments, and clarity of speech, using a scale of 4 to 5 points.

Shows Mastery of the Topic

4 Points: 22 out of 71 participants (30.99%)

5 Points: 49 out of 71 participants (69.01%)

Able to Sustain Interest in the Discussion

4 Points: 15 out of 71 participants (21.13%)

5 Points: 56 out of 71 participants (78.87%)

Welcomes Questions, Comments, and Ideas

4 Points: 22 out of 71 participants (30.99%)

5 Points: 49 out of 71 participants (69.01%)

Speaks Clearly

4 Points: 18 out of 71 participants (25.35%)

5 Points: 53 out of 71 participants (74.65%)

1. Overall Quality

The Project T.E.E.N U.P study aimed to assess the quality and effectiveness of the seminar, focusing on its overall usefulness, whether it met participants' expectations, and if the time spent was considered valuable. Participants rated these aspects using a scale of 4 to 5 points.

Results

The Seminar Will Be Useful to Me

4 Points: 35 out of 71 participants (49.30%)

5 Points: 36 out of 71 participants (50.70%)

The Seminars Met My Expectations

4 Points: 23 out of 71 participants (32.39%)

5 Points: 48 out of 71 participants (67.61%)

My Time Was Well Spent

4 Points: 29 out of 71 participants (40.85%)

5 Points: 42 out of 71 participants (59.15%)

1. Over all this seminar was

Results and Discussion

The Project T.E.E.N U.P study aimed to assess the overall quality and effectiveness of the seminar. Participants were asked to rate the seminar using a scale of 4 to 5 points.

Results

Overall, This Seminar Was:

4 Points: 7 out of 71 participants (9.86%)

5 Points: 64 out of 71 participants (90.14%)

Discussion

1. Seminar Objective

The results indicate that the seminar objectives were clearly communicated to the majority of the participants, with 57.75% rating the clarity at the highest level (5 points) and an additional 42.25% giving it a high rating (4 points). This demonstrates that the seminar organizers were successful in articulating the goals of the seminar, which is essential for ensuring that participants are aligned with the intended outcomes and can engage with the material effectively.

Regarding the attainment of the seminar objectives, the feedback was similarly positive. A significant proportion of the participants (56.34%) rated the attainment of the objectives

at the highest level (5 points), while 43.66% rated it at 4 points. This suggests that not only were the objectives clearly stated, but they were also effectively met during the seminar. The high ratings in both categories reflect the seminar's overall success in achieving its educational goals.

Overall, the seminar was well-received in terms of both clarity and effectiveness. The majority of participants felt that the objectives were clearly communicated and fully attained. This positive feedback indicates that the seminar was successful in delivering its intended content and achieving its goals. Future seminars could build on this success by maintaining clear communication of objectives and ensuring that the content is designed to fully meet these objectives for all participants. Additionally, collecting qualitative feedback could provide more detailed insights into specific areas of strength and potential improvement.

2. Seminar Content

The majority of participants (57.75%) rated the scope of the seminar content at the highest level (5 points), indicating that the content was comprehensive and met their expectations. Another 39.44% rated it 4 points, showing that most participants were satisfied. Only 2.82% rated it 3 points, suggesting a need to ensure all participants feel the content covers a broad enough range.

Quality and Clarity of Presentation

A significant number of participants (63.38%) rated the quality and clarity of the presentation as excellent (5 points), with an additional 35.21% rating it 4 points. This indicates that the presentation was well-received and effectively communicated the seminar's content. Only one participant rated it 3 points, showing a high overall satisfaction.

Organization of Topics

The organization of topics received high ratings, with 77.46% of participants giving it 5 points and 21.13% giving it 4 points. This demonstrates that the topics were well-structured and logically presented, facilitating better understanding and engagement among the participants. Only one participant rated it 3 points, reflecting general approval.

Time Allocation

Time allocation was also highly rated, with 77.46% of participants giving it 5 points and 19.72% giving it 4 points. This suggests that the time dedicated to each part of the seminar was well-balanced and appropriate for the content covered. Only 2.82% of participants rated it 3 points, indicating a strong overall satisfaction with the pacing of the seminar.

3. Facilitator

Shows Mastery of the Topic

The majority of participants (69.01%) rated the facilitator's mastery of the topic at the highest level (5 points), indicating strong confidence in the facilitator's expertise. Another 30.99% rated it 4 points, showing that most participants were satisfied with the facilitator's

knowledge. This suggests that the facilitator was well-prepared and knowledgeable about the seminar content.

Able to Sustain Interest in the Discussion

A significant number of participants (78.87%) rated the facilitator's ability to sustain their interest as excellent (5 points), with an additional 21.13% rating it 4 points. This indicates that the facilitator was engaging and able to keep the audience's attention throughout the seminar. This high level of interest suggests that the facilitator effectively used techniques to maintain engagement.

Welcomes Questions, Comments, and Ideas

The facilitator's openness to questions, comments, and ideas was rated highly, with 69.01% of participants giving it 5 points and 30.99% giving it 4 points. This reflects the facilitator's ability to create an interactive and inclusive environment, encouraging participant engagement and discussion.

Speaks Clearly

Clarity of speech received high ratings, with 74.65% of participants giving it 5 points and 25.35% giving it 4 points. This indicates that the facilitator communicated effectively, ensuring that participants could easily understand the material being presented.

4. Overall Quality

The Seminar Will Be Useful to Me

Nearly half of the participants (50.70%) rated the seminar's usefulness at the highest level (5 points), with 49.30% giving it 4 points. This indicates that the seminar was perceived as highly beneficial by the majority of participants. The close distribution between the two highest ratings suggests that the seminar content was relevant and applicable to the participants' needs.

The Seminars Met My Expectations

A significant majority of participants (67.61%) felt that the seminars met their expectations to the highest degree (5 points), while 32.39% rated it 4 points. This positive feedback indicates that the seminar successfully aligned with what participants were hoping to gain, suggesting that the objectives and outcomes were effectively communicated and achieved.

My Time Was Well Spent

Most participants (59.15%) rated their time spent in the seminar as highly valuable (5 points), with 40.85% rating it 4 points. This suggests that the participants felt their participation was worthwhile and that the seminar was an efficient use of their time. The majority high ratings reflect the overall satisfaction with the seminar's structure, content, and delivery.

5. Over All the Seminar was-

The overwhelming majority of participants (90.14%) rated the seminar at the highest level (5 points), with only 9.86% giving it 4 points. This distribution of ratings indicates a high level of satisfaction among the attendees.

High Satisfaction (5 Points)

The 64 participants who rated the seminar with 5 points highlight the seminar's exceptional quality and effectiveness. This rating suggests that the content, delivery, and overall experience of the seminar exceeded the participants' expectations. The high level of satisfaction can be attributed to various factors, including the relevance and applicability of the seminar content, the expertise of the facilitators, and the engaging presentation style.

Moderate Satisfaction (4 Points)

The 7 participants who rated the seminar with 4 points also reflect a positive experience, though with slightly less enthusiasm than those who gave it 5 points. This rating indicates that while the seminar was generally well-received, there may be areas for improvement to elevate the experience to the highest level for all participants. Potential areas for enhancement could include more interactive elements, additional practical examples, or further opportunities for participant engagement.

Conclusions

The Project T.E.E.N U.P seminar received overwhelmingly positive feedback across all assessed criteria. The majority of participants rated the seminar's objectives, content scope, presentation quality, organization, and time allocation highly. The facilitator's mastery of the topic, ability to sustain interest, welcoming attitude towards questions and comments, and clear communication were particularly praised.

Overall, the seminar was deemed highly useful, meeting or exceeding participants' expectations and being considered time well spent. With 90.14% of participants giving the seminar the highest overall rating, it is evident that the seminar was successful in delivering valuable and effective content. Moving forward, the positive feedback highlights the strengths of the seminar while also providing areas for continued enhancement to ensure all participants have an exceptional experience.

Recommendations

Based on the feedback from the Project T.E.E.N U.P seminar participants, several recommendations can be made to further enhance the quality and effectiveness of future seminars:

Maintain Clarity of Objectives:

The majority of participants (57.75%) rated the clarity of objectives highly (5 points). Continue to ensure that seminar objectives are clearly stated at the beginning to provide participants with a clear understanding of what they will achieve.

Ensure Objectives Are Fully Attained:

While 56.34% of participants felt that the objectives were fully attained (5 points), there is still room for improvement. Implement periodic checks throughout the seminar to ensure objectives are being met and address any gaps promptly.

Enhance Seminar Content Scope:

Given that 57.75% rated the scope of seminar content highly (5 points), maintaining this level of comprehensive coverage is essential. Continue to ensure that the content is broad and inclusive, covering all relevant areas.

Improve Quality and Clarity of Presentations:

With 63.38% of participants rating the presentation quality highly (5 points), it is important to continue delivering clear and well-prepared presentations. Utilizing visual aids and interactive elements can further enhance clarity and engagement.

Organize Topics Effectively:

A significant majority (77.46%) appreciated the organization of topics (5 points). Maintain this structured approach and consider participant feedback to refine the organization for even greater effectiveness.

Optimize Time Allocation:

Time management was well-received by 77.46% of participants (5 points). Continue to allocate sufficient time for each topic, ensuring a balanced and comprehensive coverage without rushing.

Facilitator Effectiveness:

Facilitators should continue to demonstrate mastery of topics, as appreciated by 69.01% of participants (5 points). Additionally, their ability to sustain interest (78.87% 5 points), welcome questions and ideas (69.01% 5 points), and speak clearly (74.65% 5 points) should be maintained and enhanced. Regular training and feedback sessions can help facilitators refine these skills.

Ensure Practical Usefulness:

The seminar's practical usefulness was highly rated by 50.70% of participants (5 points). Continue to include practical, real-world applications of seminar content to ensure it remains relevant and beneficial.

Meet Participant Expectations:

With 67.61% of participants stating the seminar met their expectations (5 points), it is crucial to maintain this standard. Collecting pre-seminar surveys to understand participant expectations can help tailor the content accordingly.

Ensure Time is Well Spent:

As 59.15% felt their time was well spent (5 points), it is important to continue delivering high-value content that justifies participants' time investment. Regularly review and update the seminar material to keep it current and engaging.

Overall Seminar Quality:

The overall seminar quality received a high rating from 90.14% of participants (5 points). Strive to maintain and build on this positive feedback by continually seeking participant input and making improvements where necessary.

By implementing these recommendations, future Project T.E.E.N U.P seminars can continue to provide high-quality, effective, and engaging learning experiences that meet the needs and expectations of all participants.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study adhered to strict ethical standards to ensure the protection of participants. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, with clear explanations provided about the study's purpose and procedures. Participants were informed of their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. To ensure anonymity, personal identifiers were removed, and confidentiality was maintained throughout the research. The well-being of participants was safeguarded by providing support resources and minimizing potential distress. The researchers declared no conflict of interest, and plagiarism was strictly avoided by proper citation of all sources. All findings were used exclusively for research purposes, ensuring the integrity and ethical conduct of the study.

Acknowledgements

The researchers would like to express their heartfelt gratitude to Dr. Joy SB Gaza, Learning Supervisor, for her invaluable guidance and support throughout the study. Our sincere appreciation extends to the Cararayan community for their enthusiastic participation and unwavering support. We are deeply grateful to the families of James Karlo Huit and Merriam Hermogeno for their generous financial and moral support, which was crucial to the successful completion of this project. Special thanks are due to the students of Cararayan National High School, whose involvement and insights were integral to the study. Above all, we acknowledge God's utmost help and guidance, which sustained us throughout this research endeavour.

REFERENCES

- Alford, S., & Morrell, C. (2019). The role of schools in preventing teenage pregnancy. *Education and Health, 37*(1), 45-50.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/03057325.2019.1578952>
- Brown, S. S., & Bzostek, S. H. (2016). Psychological impact of teenage pregnancy.

- Journal of Pediatric and Adolescent Gynecology, 29(3), 238-244.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpag.2015.11.007>
- Jaccard, J., & Dodge, T. (2014). Family dynamics and teenage pregnancy. *Family Relations*, 63(2), 223-236. <https://doi.org/10.1111/fare.12059>
- Kirby, D. (2016). The effectiveness of sex education programs. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 59(1), 2-6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jadohealth.2016.05.001>
- Kirby, D. (2018). Health outcomes of teenage pregnancy. *Public Health Reports*, 133(3), 316-325. <https://doi.org/10.1177/003335491813300306>
- Manlove, J., Mariner, C., & Romano, A. (2015). Teenage pregnancy and the achievement gap. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 56(5), 445-451.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jadohealth.2014.11.003>
- Markham, C. M., Lormand, D., & Gloppen, K. M. (2017). Peer influences on teenage pregnancy. *Journal of School Health*, 87(10), 742-749.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/josh.12532>
- Philippine Statistics Authority (2020)
- Santelli, J. S., Kantor, L. M., Grilo, S. A., Speizer, I., Lindberg, L. D., Heitel, J., Schalet, A. T., Lyon, M. E., Mason-Jones, A. J., McGovern, T., Heck, C. J., Rogers, J., & Ott, M. A. (2017). Abstinence-only-until-marriage policies and programs: An updated position paper of the Society for Adolescent Health and Medicine. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 61(3), 400-403.
- Smith, P. (2017). Socioeconomic determinants of teenage pregnancy. *Social Science & Medicine*, 188, 72-80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2017.06.014>